

***Kite Runner* and the Breakdown of Patriarchy: Scrutinizing Diversified Struggles for Sustainable Masculine Identity**

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Abstract

Existing interdisciplinary studies on masculinity have frequently focused male behaviors, bodies, and identities, but men's internal identity struggles and the influence of gendered challenges on men left largely unexplored. Lately, there has been a surge in research into masculine gender role struggles in literary contexts. Recent decades have seen a rise in research that addressed the influence of patriarchal structures on men's persistent identity challenges. This article investigates the evolving concepts of masculinity in the 21st century, focusing on the interplay of political, social, cultural, and economic forces that shape Afghan male gender norms, as depicted in Khaled Hosseini's contemporary bildungsroman, *Kite Runner* (2003). This qualitative study explores how men navigate challenging circumstances in pursuit of masculine ideals, examining the various pressures shaping men's daily identity battles within the context of Afghanistan before, during, and after the Taliban's rise to power. Moreover, the analysis investigates the novel's portrayal of literary masculinities and explores whether these representations reflect significant shifts in the construction of male identity within Afghan culture.

Keywords: Male Identity, Patriarchy, Gender Roles, Identity Construction, The Orient, Power Relations, Patriarchal Pressure, Bildungsroman

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Masculinity Studies and the Depiction of Masculinity in Kite Runner

Kite Runner (2003) follows Amir, a young Afghan who comes from a privileged Afghan background, and whose life experiences, including his eventual relocation to the United States, are shaped by the tumultuous backdrop of Afghanistan, including the rise of the Taliban. The novel centers on Amir's emotional journey as he navigates his relationship with his father Baba. Hosseini explores both the themes and facets of masculinity and social dynamics within Eastern societies, examining the status and challenges faced by men. Through the representation of male characters in the novel, this article unfolds across three distinct periods seen through Amir's perspective: the portrayal of his idyllic childhood preceding the Taliban's rise, and subsequently, the traumatic events that irrevocably alter his life. The narrative also highlights the pivotal relationship between Amir and Hassan. The second part of the novel depicts the arrival of the Taliban in Kabul, leading to Baba and Amir's forced migration to the United States. Finally, the narrative culminates in Amir's adulthood in the U.S, including his return to Kabul and Pakistan to save Sohrab, Hassan's son, from the Taliban's control.

The novel leads to the elaboration of complicated and nonlinear dynamics where conflicts are set. Amir's change from a betrayer to a savior and finally pursuing the ideal bond with his father by gaining his father's respect as a "male-author" can be shown as evidence for the functionality of the bildungsroman. In the same way, one of the striking features of the bildungsroman is that the genre deals with the character's integration with himself and the environment while displaying realization-maturation processes: "There is a way to be good again" (pp.168) This influential quote in the novel summarizes his transformation from guilt to redemption. Thus, Hosseini's Kite Runner delineates the bildungsroman genre by contributing to the protagonist's quest for identity.

According to Hobbs (2013) in *Masculinity Studies and Literature*, men's studies are the forerunners of literary masculinity studies, drawing on theoretical paradigms from feminist research. Similarly, the *Handbook of Studies on Men and Masculinities*, edited by Kimmel, Connell, and Hearn (2005), suggests that masculinity is explored in literature in a variety of ways. Raewyn Connell uses three criteria to characterize masculinity: dominant, complicit, and submissive. Hegemonic masculinity and dominant masculinity are often used interchangeably. It may be argued that both represent a way of acting and behaving that confers and maintains dominance for men in a certain society. Connell's theory is based on Gramsci's idea of hegemony, arguing that rather than coming from terror, the power that specific displays of masculinity produce is decided by others' approval and acknowledgment of them. As a result, both terms address the range of masculinities and the power struggles that exist within the same gender group. In *Masculinities*, Connell argues that there is always a "hegemonic masculinity" in a culture, regardless of the other masculinities that exist within it. This can be defined as the standard by which members of that particular civilization are appraised in terms of their masculinity.

There appears to be consensus on what constitutes a socially acceptable masculinity performance, especially in the Orient. Berg (2016) focuses on the male challenge as "it is not the traits themselves that are interesting but rather the struggle between the articulated expectations and individual men's way of meeting the expectations depending on their position and background." Berg's idea highlights how a particular character reacts and deals with societal expectations. It suggests that the interesting

thing to consider is not the traits of men themselves, but how men deal with these expectations. More openly, when linked with the men vs. men power relationship in *Kite Runner*, it becomes apparent that the struggle is the struggle between the expectation, the individual's reaction to the expectations and how they interact with each other. This particular theoretical statement also underlines the fact that emphasizes the importance of understanding of how men deal with their identity, their actions, and the expectations of their society. In addition, it highlights the idea that different men experience these expectations differently, shaped by their roles, status, and experiences. As the context of masculine struggle is the struggle between the two (Amir and Hassan) the differences in their behaviors, though they share many things, are due to their very different social positions. Amir is a great example of how individual men react to the struggle between expectations and the reality of their lives. In this respect, this quote is relevant because it underscores how the characters' actions are not only reflections of their behavior but also examples of how they are reacting to the different things in the novel. The actions of each character show the ways they are struggling with their identity. An engaging quote from *Kite Runner* exemplifies the struggle between individual expectations and reality. Baba says: “A boy who won’t stand up for himself becomes a man who can’t stand up for anything” (pp.221) emphasizes the potential consequences of not conforming to masculine expectations by encapsulating the central struggle of male identity crisis in the novel.

In terms of societal constructs and the performance of manhood in *Kite Runner*, it can be stated that the novel offers a compelling exploration of masculinity, intricately woven with the threads of gendered behavior and the broader societal and cultural frameworks that define Afghan male identity. Through the narrative voice of Amir, the novel illuminates the processes by which individuals are shaped by, and in turn, navigate the prescriptive expectations of manhood. *Kite Runner* delves into the societal values that shape the notion of what a “grown man” should aspire to become, in turn portraying masculinity as a source of both prestige and power. Hosseini's narrative emphasizes the powerful impact of the patriarchal requirements of masculinity. The novel is not just a story of individual experience but a commentary on the ways in which these expectations can both empower and constrain, creating a complex web of expectations and, at times, internal conflict. The novel's strength lies in its nuanced portrayal of both masculine and anti-masculine characteristics, challenging the reader to consider the complexities of male identity. Hosseini strategically employs the first-person narration to provide an intimate examination of how masculinity is experienced and performed within the cultural context of Afghanistan. This narrative perspective allows for a critical examination of how men “construct” their own understanding of manhood. By analyzing the interplay of these internal factors, Hosseini offers a profound commentary on the formation and consequences of adhering to or resisting the imposed ideals of Afghan masculinity. This exploration, from Amir's subjective viewpoint, provides a rich context in which the interplay between societal pressure and individual agency is given attention.

Through the evocative narration of Amir, Hosseini, masterfully dissects the societal pressures that shape the performance of masculinity within the Afghan context. The following excerpt poignantly illustrates the clash between paternal expectation and individual inclination: "fathering a son who preferred burying his face in poetry books to hunting...well, that wasn't how Baba envisioned it, I suppose" (p. 19). This seemingly simple observation reveals the deeply ingrained framework of

hegemonic masculinity, highlighting how it defines acceptable forms of male expression and social standing within Afghan culture. The protagonist's internal struggle serves as a crucial lens through which Hosseini illuminates Baba's, and by extension, Afghan society's construction of hegemonic masculinity. The preference for poetry over hunting becomes a site of profound disappointment, signaling a deviation from the prescribed path of strength, physical prowess, and dominance expected of a male heir. This divergence underscores how the cultural system imposes a rigid set of criteria that dictates what constitutes a “sustainable” man, and by extension, what is perceived as a “failure” to live up to these ideals. Hosseini employs Amir's perspective to reveal the sharp, often unforgiving terms by which masculinity is judged. The author critiques the societal tendency to marginalize and devalue those who do not conform to the prescribed masculine norms. In contrast, idealized masculine traits—strength, courage, and assertiveness—with Amir's perceived weaknesses, the novel exposes male power dynamics inherent in the construction of hegemonic masculinity in the Afghan culture. The novel explores the interplay of hegemonic and subordinate models of masculinity by presenting characters like Baba, who embody the dominant ideals. And through characters like Amir, who struggle to conform, Hosseini displays readers to confront the complexities of these hierarchical structures. This narrative strategy allows a ground for critical examination of how the pursuit of authority and respect, often associated with hegemonic masculinity, shapes individual experiences and, by extension, the wider social landscape. The novel's power resides in its ability to render these complex dynamics as the source of both internal conflict and interpersonal relationships.

Research on masculinity has consistently highlighted the intricate power dynamics that underlie male experiences and interactions. Studies have demonstrated that traditional notions of masculinity are not universally applicable, but rather are shaped by cultural, social, and economic contexts. The concept of patriarchy serves as a framework for understanding how societal structures perpetuate and reinforce masculine norms, contributing to the construction and performance of masculinity. To grasp the ways in which men establish and maintain their masculine authority, it is essential to delve into the cultural nuances that shape these dynamics, illuminating the complex interplay between individual and collective expressions of masculinity. Historian Gerda Lerner offers a valuable perspective on the historical construction of masculinity. In her book *The Creation of Patriarchy* (1987), Lerner provides a framework to analyze the historical construction of patriarchy as a system of organizing society. Lerner argues that patriarchy is a historical product that has been a product of history. She aims to trace the emergence of patriarchal norms. She meticulously examines the patriarchal power structures, and their formation and historical evolution in Mesopotamia and Abrahamic regions. In her research, Lerner draws attention to the continuum of men's pervasive domination. According to her, patriarchy has become the socially normalized, a cross-culturally accepted status quo. Prior to the 1960s, societal perceptions of manhood and its associated advantages and disadvantages remained largely unchallenged. The prevailing social climate, marked by women's activism for gender equality, did not necessarily prompt scrutiny of men's status. The 1980s witnessed a significant shift with the burgeoning field of masculinity studies. Researchers utilized Antonio Gramsci's concept of “hegemony” to analyze the various expressions of masculinity and their relationship to power and social control. This framework helped to explain how certain forms of masculinity become dominant. Through exploring diverse forms of masculinity and marginalized experiences of men, the research

contributed to more nuanced understanding of men's social identities across a range of cultural contexts.

Literary studies provide a valuable lens on an extended analysis on the profound effects of patriarchy on the construction of masculinities within the landscape of gender politics. Scholars who contribute on gender issues and the intricate portrayal of patriarchal structures significantly spot light on the connection to the interdisciplinary aspects of masculinity. Peter N. Stearns (1990) challenges the established view, arguing that “masculinity is a constant contradictory struggle rather than just a privileged position.” This perspective complicates the traditional, often rigid, notions of masculinity. Applying this idea, the novel explores the complex dynamics of masculinity that exist on a collective basis, and in turn, their potential for destructive consequences by focusing on father-son relationships. Patriarchy’s influence is exerted through rigid ideologies. Through Hosseini's characterizations, the text highlights how male figures are often compelled, from a young age, to conform to patriarchal structures, which reinforce traditional norms. For instance, the kite-running competition, a central motif, exemplifies how boys are pressured to demonstrate their masculinity, simultaneously acting as a means of identity formation.

Chauvinism is a dominant theme in the novel, exemplifying the pervasive effects of patriarchal upbringing that prioritize power and dominance. Türkoğlu & Cingöz-Ulu (2019) argue that men are often expected to demonstrate their dominance within patriarchal systems. Furthermore, they suggest that gender is a complex, relational, and culturally constructed concept that influences the distribution of power and desire. Existing research highlights the significance of examining traditional patriarchal practices and their impact on mental health, particularly anxiety-related issues. Hegemonic masculinity represents the dominant ideology of societal expectations, dictating norms and behaviors that define what it means to be a "real man." This ideology, as noted by Thompson & Bennet (2015) and Thompson and Pleck (1986), emphasizes emotional self-control and competition as essential components of masculine identity. The pressure to conform to these culturally created and enforced standards traps men, limiting their individuality and subjecting them to patriarchal expectations. The result is a narrow definition of manhood that stifles emotional expression and reinforces oppressive norms. The heart of the novel beats with Amir's captivating journey: a metamorphosis from a boy lost in innocence to a man forged in the fires of experience. Through Amir's own words, the narrative paints a vivid picture of this evolution. We meet him first as a boy cloaked in isolation, haunted by insecurities and the weight of perceived "anti-masculine features." *Could these perceived "anti-masculine features" be a product of the rigid cultural expectations, the suffocating confines of traditional masculinity, that the novel recounts. The story charts his quest for self-actualization, a path paved with introspection. In his telling, Amir's boyhood years are a tapestry woven with confusion, fear, and a stifled voice, set against Hassan's unwavering courage and goodness. Is Hassan's unwavering loyalty and seemingly effortless adherence to societal expectations a foil, highlighting the pressure Amir feels to conform, and perhaps revealing the subtly destructive nature of societal expectations and chauvinism? This internal conflict, amplified by Baba's detached demeanor, fuels the central tension of the story. Baba's preference for Hassan and his apparent disapproval of Amir's perceived weaknesses could be seen as a manifestation of internalized chauvinism, a reinforcement of the dominant male ideal and a rejection of anything that deviates from it. It's a relationship strained

by unspoken expectations, a cultural climate where vulnerability is a weakness and emotional needs go unmet. This absence of emotional validation, especially from a father, can be directly tied to the pressure to conform to patriarchal norms, which is often a central theme in critical discussions of chauvinism.

Islamist, Muslim and Military Masculine Challenges in Kite Runner

Masculine gender dichotomies represented in the novel are multifaceted and diverse. Therefore, masculine gender privileges associated with maleness need to be exposed and addressed in terms of independent and collective creation of masculinities in Hosseini's depiction. In this section, muslim masculinities and the traditional representations of Islamist masculinity will be differentiated and discussed in reference to the novel. While the second type is more indicative of how masculinities are constructed in Muslim nations, the former is more of a category that is acknowledged by others. To begin with, it can be argued that the emergence of markers of Afghan masculinity require sustainability. With the Taliban invasion as Hosseini depicts, men's honor is threatened and each man in the novel becomes subservient to another male figure during the invasion.

The essence of masculine traits in the Afghan context as visible in the quote are institutionalized and internalized by virtue and Amir's narrative might represent real-life examples of hegemonic masculinity. Baba's representation becomes more diffused and paralyzed during and after the Taliban. Among these variations of depicted masculinities, far from representing the Afghan ideal man, Baba's portrayal of physical and moral struggle gain significance. His pursuit of masculine attributes is weakened and he commits himself for survival. He eventually decides to plan their getaway for survival. Baba and Amir get into a pickup and drive out of Kabul for Jalalabad and finally to California, U.S.A where these two characters meet with the Western frame of masculinity. Interestingly, Hosseini's unique depiction of Baba's non-religious masculine character draws a contrast; as he says: "If there's a God out there, then I would hope he has more important things to attend to than my drinking scotch or eating pork" (p.14). In the hegemonic Afghan masculine system, Baba's quest and mockery can be explained with phenomenical cultural variations of masculinity. It becomes apparent that exceptionally masculinity is more influenced by economic conditions than religious beliefs.

Eichler (2014) has pinned that military masculinities has been described as "the privileging of violence and other masculine norms and behaviours valued by martial institutions. A recent research conducted by Ahsan&Tirmizi (2021) reveals that since the Taliban's founding, the Taliban's essentialized interpretation of Islamic piety and Afghan Pashtun honor codes, or pashtunwali, has influenced masculinities. Edwards (2017) has defined pashtunwali as "an extremely diverse set of codes and practices, and "cultural conceptual space in which identity is negotiated" In line with this definition, in Kite Runner (2003) Hosseini portrays Afghanistan as diverse and a multiethnic nation, so do masculinity codes. Thus, the struggle of Afghan men depicted in the novel might be constantly effected by military masculinities deeply nurtured by tough patriarchal codes attributed to men.

In order to identify the masculine struggle in Kite Runner, it is found out that religion, basically Islam and pashtunwali dictate specific honor rules, and adherence to patriarchal standards is essential to the development of masculine identities. As Mosawi demonstrates (2019) "a man without honor, is no

man at all” This quote reveals the study by Echavez et al (2016) how Afghan men are confined to a position of humiliation when they violate the honorable rules of men. Likewise in the novel, Baba’s ideology about achieving manhood draws a parallel: Amir’s insights about manhood creates a struggle as his recounts about his father’s manhood makes masculine traits are unattainable for him. His depiction of Baba as “he can drop the devil to his knees begging for mercy,” (p.14) can be characterized as a strong male role model, particularly for Amir, who is raised in a house full of guys. From Amir's viewpoint, Baba's manhood can be further defined as a mythologized type of masculinity. As a result, Amir takes his distance and this lowers his social and masculine standing. According to Chiovenda (2020), men who deviate from the societal norms of acceptable masculine conduct frequently face severe consequences in the form of social disapproval which adversely impacts their and their family's claims to dignity and respectability. He continues to show how this idea of inferior masculinity can be the source of struggle and passed down from father to son. Particularly, the conflict between Baba and Amir in terms of unfulfilled masculine expectations can be analysed respectively since Baba’s constant masculine expectations from Amir produce pressure and stress between them. It is explicit that Amir’s pursuit of masculine identity do not match the codes for Afghan masculinities, Military or otherwise, masculine codes are constantly reproduced which create crisis.

For a considerable amount of time, feminist academics have argued that military masculinities are produced in conjunction with other identities and are inherently flexible and dynamic (Higate 2003). “Afghan” or “Afghanistan” misrepresent the ways in which ethnicities and cultural trends shape masculine attitude; at worst, it could characterize and stereotype a very broad range of phenomena. According to Connell, (2005) depending on various identities (race, age, socioeconomic situation, religion, etc.), different men experience different effects and exhibit distinct masculine features. Demetriou (2001) argues that even the most "hegemonic" manifestations of masculinity—idealized acts of aggression, domination, virility, etc.—that denigrate other attributes of masculinity are in competition with other attractive ways to be a man. Even individual men constantly reshape their masculinities in response to external social influences, and they take on new identities when they relocate from one place to another. Although there are broad patterns in the way that masculinities are built in Afghanistan, and conflict plays a significant role in this process, masculinities are also invariably relational, intersectional, and situationally constructed.

Discussion

Kite Runner (2003), written by Khaled Hosseini, a prolific Afghan-American author, aligns with the bildungsroman genre and can be best described as a narrative of emotional development and maturation of Amir, an Afghan-American man. Bildungsroman as a specific literary genre has an essential place in gender studies. Via the representation of Amir, it becomes clear to literally identify both the cross-cultural differences of the Eastern and Western male frame, and how they differ in masculinity by compelling and depiction of masculine gender norms. As defined by Lynch (2010), bildungsroman explores the protagonist's journey to self-awareness and maturity which requires navigating societal expectations, personal conflicts, and familial bonds. This particular genre is firmly embedded in unique cultural contexts, frequently reflecting the social and historical conditions of the time. Lynch examines how these environments shape characters' development and sense of self.

Typically, *Kite Runner* as an exemplar of bildungsroman, comprises a number of hurdles and crises that the protagonist must face and conquer in order to achieve personal transformation. These conflicts are critical to character development and sheds light on gender based thematic depth. Lynch defines the bildungsroman not only as a narrative framework, but also as a reflection of larger existential concerns, highlighting the difficulty of growing up in a changing environment. It has been observed that such literary investigation of personal and societal processes expand the readers' comprehension of literature.

Kite Runner opens with a call to Amir, a successful Afghan-American writer, from his father's former friend Rahim Khan in Pakistan. This call triggers a flashback, transporting the reader to Amir's childhood in Afghanistan, when he was twelve. There, he and Hassan, a Hazara boy who is both his playmate and servant, grow up together. The narrative gradually reveals Amir's past guilt, stemming from his betrayal of Hassan. Rahim Khan's summon compels Amir to confront his past transgressions, specifically his silence following Hassan's assault by Assef.

Kite Runner can be considered as a model for diasporic literature since the novel involves the sense of loss and alienation that result from displacement or the forced migration of a father and the son from their native land. The novel equally displays an exemplar of diasporic literature by addressing themes of displacement, existential unsettlement, sentimentality, and identity exploration. Lau (2009) states that that while diasporic writers connect with the Orient by ethnicity, and in terms of language, they enjoy "a position of power and dominance" owing to their location outside of what she addresses "the Orient". Linked with these literary tools, it can be argued that Hosseini exhibits different facets of masculinity who are pushed to the limits of violence and aggression linked with power. Using Lau's viewpoint, it can be argued that Hosseini's portrayal of Afghanistan and its men perpetuates the Orient, further a call for the marginalization of the region and its people by Talibanization. Hosseini's portrayal of exploited native land via the display of various masculinity representations not only portrays a period of political instability due to Taliban attacks but also mirrors the vicious cycle of patriarchy produced and reproduced in this particular region.

Masculinity Studies in Literature and Depictions of Dynamic Masculine Struggle in the Orient: *Kite Runner*

Owing to existing literary gender studies, Masculinity Studies shed light on the circumstances that lead to men's transformation or the reasons behind men's crises. Since existing research move toward diversity of maleness and masculinities change across time, some historical periods (as Hosseini has portrayed the Taliban invasion in *Kite Runner*) are more traumatic for men than others. These crisis situations could involve changes in men's status, income, or even country (the forced migration case in *Kite Runner*), all of which have been depicted as the potential to influence the structures of masculinity.

American scholar Eve Sedgwick had a strong interest in post-structuralist literary and cultural representations on masculinity. In her work, *The Epistemology of the Closet* (1990) she marks that masculinity is a multifaceted phenomena that always evolves and changes. Likewise, researcher Stefan Horlacher voices out that literature can reveal the hidden and the difficult facets of masculinity that are not always evident in day-to-day interactions. Therefore, the study of masculinity should be

regarded as a crucial area of investigation in literary fiction analysis to explore the cultural genesis in a particular context. One of the pivotal pioneers of the field, Kimmel (1996) pins that “one must accept the plurality of the paradigm in masculinity” to explore the male struggle.

The impression of masculinity theories in literature gained momentum largely due to the work of sociologist R.W. Connell. This article takes its turn from Raewyn Connell's hegemonic masculinity model both as a tool and a framework to comprehend masculine struggle and the challenging ways of masculinity in *Kite Runner*. In particular, her concept of "hegemonic masculinity" is widely regarded as the most influential theoretical concept in the history of the study of men and masculinity. Her seminal work *Masculinities* (1995) expands upon the power dynamics existing amongst various masculinity types. Connell classifies the term as “the relations between the different kinds of masculinity: relations of alliance, dominance and subordination.” It can be argued that Connell’s definition of these relationships are valid in *Kite Runner* male characters with Baba, Amir, Hassan, Rahim Khan, Ali and Assef. It has been observed that each of these characters struggle not only with the ideals of patriarchy but also with each other in terms of masculine gender norms. More openly, I would like to draw attention to the depictions of these struggling characters with changing conceptions of masculinity that put them in a “contestable position” in the East. This phrase should be explored to identify different tenets constituted by masculine ideals, and the following quote can be given as an example to how male characters’ challenge vary and intertwined in the pursuit of masculinity. “I was going to win, and I was going to run that last kite. Then I would bring it home and show it to Baba. Show him once and for all that his son was worthy” (p.60) From a masculine ideal standpoint, it may be stated that Amir is presented as constantly suffering from insufficiency in terms of male gender norms. His uneasy attitudes during the kite running race (due to his desire to be completely present in his father's eyes as a boy) makes him feel emotionally under pressure for not being enough competent for maleness. Goyal (2023) states that: “Hegemonic masculinity builds pressure on young boys and even on those grown-up men who are different from the societal "ideal" men and inadvertently makes them believe that they lack masculinity.” As a result of this perceived lack of masculinity, "toxic masculinity" appears, a term which refers to destructive effects and it has an impact on other men around them. It is typical to reduce the complexity of masculinities to toxic and crisis-related issues. Amir’s lack in his sense of maleness originates from his father’s continuous ignoring views of him.

Messner (1992) suggests that men may even compete with one another to demonstrate their power by triumphing in challenging or conflictual situations as a way of upholding the values of masculine honor. A striking example of masculine struggle depicted in the novel can be shown as an example of Amir’s detachment and how traditional masculine norms force men emotionally. One such instance happens during the Buzkashi tournament, a violent competition among Afghan men. A chapandaz is a local term coined for a horseman, who tries to drop a goat carcass into an assigned circle while being attacked by other horseman:

But at the moment, I watched with horror as one of the chapandaz fell off his saddle and was trampled under a score of hooves. His body was tossed and hurled in the stampede like a rag doll, finally rolling to a stop when the melee moved on. He twitched once and lay motionless, his legs bent at unnatural angles, a pool of his blood soaking through the sand. I began to cry. I

cried all the way back home. I remember how Baba's hands clenched around the steering wheel. Clenched and unclenched. Mostly, I will never forget Baba's valiant efforts to conceal the disgusted look on his face as he drove in silence. (pp.20)

It is explicitly clear that, in the Afghan context of masculinity, men are encouraged to participate in tough and violent sports that are competitive and solely reserved for men. Cancian (1987) defines “tough,” a sign of strength and is encouragement” and the word is associated with man and masculinity. Furthermore, being emotionally vulnerable is frowned upon and, can even result in social rejection since it is thought that displaying these kinds of feelings detracts from a man's masculinity. Hosseini narrates Baba’s avoidance through “disgusted look” to highlight typical Afghan masculine ideology when masculine traits are not fulfilled. Amir’s despair and his act of crying is denied or addressed as a “lack of manliness” after witnessing “a pool of blood”. His attitude is ignored by his father and the masculine display of violence for strength is normalised in this particular culture.

By putting various references to manliness through Baba’s glance, Hosseini portrays Amir’s disconnection from ideal masculine profile which is parallel to what Connell argues: “Young boys are under pressure from hegemonic masculinity, which unintentionally leads them to feel that they are not "real men" or that they lack masculinity. Furthermore, according to Baba, Amir’s interest in literature is not within the Orient scope of masculinity therefore inadmissible in Afghan norms of masculinity. Performing masculinity is accepted as a brand in the Orient and during his boyhood Amir is not nominated, and is not favoured by Baba as he constantly fails in representing the norms of masculinity from his father’s point of view:

“but fathering a son who preferred burying his face in poetry books to hunting well, that wasn't how Baba had envisioned it, I suppose. Real men didn't read poetry – and God forbid they should ever write it! Real men – real boys – played soccer just as Baba had when he had been young... He signed me up for soccer teams to stir the same passion in me. But I was pathetic, a blundering liability to my own team. (pp. 19)

The quote clearly shows how Hosseini delves into presenting the ambiguous and incoherent definitions of masculinity in the context of father-son relationship. Although Amir makes efforts to get close to his father with the goal of learning from him about manhood and, eventually, receive his respect to establish a sustainable father-son relationship, his efforts fail. The paradox between the two validates the existing hegemonic struggle within the Afghan masculine dynamics. More closely, Baba both stands for ultimate symbol for maleness and power and at the same time the source of isolation and disconnection from masculinity. Amir's endeavor to get the respect and affection of his father ends tragically as in the eyes of his father there are two cornerstones of manhood are honor and pride: "The man is a Pashtun to the root. He has nang and namoos. Nang. Namooos. Honor and pride. The tenets of Pashtun men.” (pp. 134). The paradox in Baba's discourse is that, in addition to ultimately ruining his own honor, he contradicts himself by having an affair with Sanaubar, Ali’s wife and keeps it as a secret. Hosseini portrays Afghan masculine exercise from an Oriental perspective that masculine reputation is not a supremacy but a paradoxical situation where men suffer. Hosseini highlights the domains of patriarchal confinement and underlines the fact that hegemonic masculinity

is a toxic situation with Baba's teachings about honesty and integrity as the cornerstones of male attributes in the Orient.

Another prominent example of masculine struggle in the Orient appears with men who are expected to control their emotions when the same sex group is close. In *The Myth of Masculinity*, Pleck (1981) makes it clear that it's an emotional condition where one's gender-based behavioral expectations have a negative impact on both the person and people around them. While reflecting masculinity ideals and the dominance over other men in the Orient, Hosseini not only highlights the detrimental effects of hegemonic masculinity in the cultural context but also aims to demonstrate how Oriental masculine norms limit and exploit men. It is visible that Hosseini presents how masculinity is reduced to a package composed of a set of features, through his depiction of the protagonist Amir, and displays the division and the roles attributed to men in Afghan society. Macho is the term that stands for the paradox that is linked with masculinity and male gender norm in the Orient. It symbolizes strength and forbids acknowledging or expressing feelings that would be interpreted as unmanly or anti-masculine. Throughout the novel, Hosseini constantly illustrates the shifting conceptions of masculinity and the challenges associated with its performance through the first-person male narrator, Amir. The narrative agrees on a set of fundamental qualities summed up in a hegemonic ideal of masculinity as the capacity to provide and protect, despite variations in how masculinity is presented with respect to a specific culture.

Hosseini portrays Amir as a noble Pashtun boy, a son to a notable Afghan Merchant who wishes to achieve the ideals of maleness but voices Orient type of masculine struggle. In Connell's terms, Amir can be considered as a boy who perceives masculinity as a marginalized sphere that relies on authorization. In other words, masculinity is regarded as a valuable possession limited to powerful men. Thus, the description for the men in the Orient requires assertiveness, aggressiveness, dominance, and steadfastness in the face of threats or misfortune. These qualities emphasize strength and discourages the expression of emotions, including vulnerability or a plea for aid like Amir's case. Strength, honor, and sustainable action have become to represent and constitute ideal masculinity to fulfill Oriental pursuit of maleness accompanied by patriarchal power in this particular context.

Hobbs (2013) in *Masculinity Studies and Literature* suggests that Men's studies, which in turn draw upon and owe many of the theoretical models employed to feminist study, are the ancestors of literary masculinity studies. Similarly, In *Handbook of Studies on Men and Masculinities* edited by Kimmel, Connell and Hearn (2005) it has been suggested that in literature, masculinity is approached in a variety of ways. Three categories dominant, complicit, and submissive are used by Connell to classify masculinity. Hegemonic masculinity and "dominant masculinity" are terms that are frequently used interchangeably. It might be claimed to represent an approach to acting and behaving that grants and preserves power for men in a certain society. Connell has based her argument on Antonio Gramsci's definition of hegemony, contending that rather than stemming from terror, the power that particular manifestations of masculinity produce is determined by others' approval and acknowledgment of it. Therefore, the diversity of masculinities and the power struggles they face within the same sex group. Connell contends in *Masculinities* that there is always a "hegemonic masculinity" in a culture, regardless of the multitude of masculinities that occur within it. This is an ideal against which members of that specific society are judged in terms of their masculinities. There appears to be

agreement on what constitutes a socially acceptable masculinity performance particularly in the Orient. Berg (2016) examines the masculine challenge as “it is not the traits themselves that are interesting but rather the struggle between the articulated expectations and individual men’s way of meeting the expectations depending on their position and background.” This particular masculine paradox exists in the frame of dominance when men try to challenge the other men’s masculinity in order to sustain superiority and honor. While examining the construction and application of literary masculinities, Hosseini seeks to address how masculine ideals are formulated, the functioning of the system and the sustainability of these masculinities in the novel.

Connell's theory of hegemonic masculinity is used to analyze the novel's content and literary masculinities in this article. The idea emphasizes a hierarchy among various masculinities while also acknowledging their diversity. Connell emphasizes the binary contradiction between masculine and non-masculine traits. This is especially relevant to this article as it filters the comprehension of the prescribed masculinities through the voices of male characters. To some extent, masculine struggle originates from the perspective of the masculine characters. Furthermore, it has been observed that male characters acquire, produce, reflect and re-shape masculinity in different cultural frameworks. For instance, Amir narrates the way society views a grown man who is expected to rise constantly in prestige and power. The author presents male masculinity and anti-masculine features in order to investigate how masculinity is practiced in accordance with the male voice. While giving emphasis on the patriarchal requirements of masculinity, Hosseini illustrates ‘men’s construction of men’ through the first person narrator Amir via the male-gender conflict he encounters with his father Baba. Through the depiction of Amir, Hosseini sheds light on the sharp limits of masculinity who is presented as vulnerable and insufficient to carry out any masculine activity in a way that is socially acceptable. By portraying the elements of hegemonic masculinity which are typically perceived as bestowing authority and respect, the author explores the subordinate models of masculinity versus the idolised.

Linked with the argument above, Peter N. Stearns (1990) argues that "masculinity is a constant contradictory struggle rather than just a privileged position" which is against the institutionalized and firmly structured notions of masculinity. Referring to the quote, it can be stated that the novel deals with different patterns of masculinity in masculine dynamics that exist on a collective basis and has destructive effects in father-son and Talibanist masculine depictions. Since patriarchy imposes harsh and unquestionable ideologies, throughout Hosseini’s different male character depictions, it can be understood that from childhood onwards, male characters are forced into masculine patterns that reinforce traditional norms about men. For example, kite running is presented as an arena for boys to prove their masculinity to be recognized by others. Exaggerating the notions of manhood avoid men from exploring themselves and put them at risk of being victims in the Orient. On top of that, it has been observed that men from a Talibanist masculine view, masculinity takes a new curve and men are pushed to the limits of violence and aggression with provoking brutality. Patriarchy in this sense is restructured and becomes a vicious cycle where men become the target and constantly victimized by the system.

In the Eastern context, it is clear that men who combat the supremacy are more prone to destructive masculinity. In the Afghan social context, it is required and allowable to use violence to pursue

masculine power. Often narrated briefly in the novel, the need to uphold masculine honor can even spark male tournaments to demonstrate their strength. Triumphant under such circumstances involve a dispute or difficulty and male figures who are displayed in the novel have difficulty to project emotions are negatively addressed. Thus facing the threat of being ignored or false-labelled produces more destructive representations. Throughout their lives, they have to combat struggle to perform by avoiding their emotions to hide their inner conflicts. In the domain of toxic masculinity, Taliban stands for military masculinity that Afghan men have to face. Due to Taliban's extreme and violent actions in Afghanistan, Hosseini highlights the shifting masculine terms which are refigured, reproduced and the male authority appears distorted. More openly, masculinity in the Orient is often associated and intertwined with the ideals of power and authority but Taliban militarism by itself can be considered as to have destructive influence on masculinity and manliness. Therefore Hosseini not only explores the typical masculinity struggle of the men in the Orient but also demonstrates how those men suffer Talibanist enforced views on Orient masculinity as well. The portrayal of masculine struggle under a fist of extreme masculine authority, men's struggle with masculinity is doubled and changes the course of masculine agenda. Throughout the novel, civil Afghan male characters regardless of origin have to face the abuses and have been plagued by the Taliban militarist masculine authority. Hosseini's depiction of Amir and his father, depiction of Taliban by Amir evidently underlines distinct features of manliness and masculinity.

The novel draws a descriptive agenda through Amir's narration as the protagonist. In the beginning, Amir is depicted as an isolated boy who suffers for his anti-masculine features such as discouragement and selfishness. His reinterpretation of experience to pursue self-actualization is the plot of the novel. Through his narration, Amir's boyhood years are depicted full of confusion, fear and inability to express himself versus Hassan's courage, fearlessness and goodness. Amir's contradiction is continuously provoked by Amir's father's neglectful manners. Since Baba encourages Hassan more than Amir, his attitude raises the tension between them. Actually, it can be said that Amir's insecurities about their relationship with his father is rooted in Baba's distant and cold nature towards him. This also has to do with the cultural norms where feelings are hidden and Amir's emotional commitment to his father is unrequited. The relationship of Baba and Amir cannot be considered as a rewarding one during Amir's childhood. Amir's needs are substituted by Rahim Khan instead of Baba.

The misuse and the misinterpretation of different types of masculinities drives Amir to helplessness, disappointment and frustration during boyhood. Not to be stagnated of being weak or off the limits of masculinity, Amir is forced to present a tough masculine mindset targeted at men to become a distinguishable member of Afghan society. Thus, Amir's struggle for his father's approval fails and Hosseini draws attention to the significance of the empathetic bond in such dynamics. Unlike his father, Amir is not into athletics, silent and unwilling to join other boys in martial arts. He is presented as a boy mostly occupied with poetry and passionate with writing stories like his mother. Baba doesn't fancy such occupations which do not make sense for him and says **"If I hadn't seen the doctor pull him out of my wife with my own eyes, I'd never believe he's my son"** (p. 25). Amir's need for paternal connection and his will unite with him in the domestic sphere is presented as highly problematic where the reader is introduced to two common features of patriarchy. The term patriarchy

refers to the rule of the father where all kinds of emotional expressions are identified with weakness and submissiveness.

Conclusion

Afghan-American novelist Khaled Hosseini has endeavored to expose the agony inflicted by Taliban attacks on Afghanistan in the late 1990s through his debut novel, *Kite Runner* (2003). The novel explores how Afghan society reinforces patriarchal norms and hegemonic masculinity, moving away from egalitarian male ideals. Hosseini introduces the first-person male narrator, Amir, to depict altering ideals of masculinity and the patriarchal obstacles connected with its performance in the . *Kite Runner* (2003) by Khaled Hosseini is a powerful and poignant novel that calls attention to the complexities of Afghan male identity in the face of societal change and the gradual decline of patriarchal norms. Set against the backdrop of Afghanistan's tumultuous history, the novel masterfully weaves together themes of tradition, culture, and masculine struggle, offering a profound exploration of the men's construction of identity. Through Amir's and Hassan's story readers can witness the intricate dance between masculinity and femininity, tradition and modernity, and the tensions that arise from the clashing of these forces. This article highlights a literary quest to examine the struggles of male identity in *Kite Runner*. By scrutinizing the novel's depiction of Afghan male identity, one can explore the ways in which patriarchal norms are challenged and eventually give way to a more nuanced understanding of masculinity.

Through this analysis, it has been observed that the phenomenon of masculinity is a multifaceted entity, with distinct manifestations in Eastern and Western societies. At its core, patriarchal ideologies in both cultures are built upon a foundation of domination, power, and control - a phenomenon that transcends geographical boundaries. It has consistently shown that the rigid expectations of dominant masculine ideologies create anxiety-ridden environments for men, as they feel pressured to conform to societal norms. This emphasis on status and tradition can have devastating consequences for men, eroding their emotional well-being and sense of self-worth. The constraints of traditional masculinity can be suffocating, limiting men's ability to express themselves authentically and fostering a culture of silence and repression. This is exemplified in the novel where Amir's internalized shame and struggle to live up to societal expectations are deeply tied to the cultural pressures of traditional masculinity.

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